

PREPARING STUDENTS FOR PISA STUDIES IN GRADE 7-9 IN
GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS.

Raxmonov Sherzod Tolibovich

Tashkent State Technical University

Independent researcher Pedagogical profession

Tel . 997056171

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Abstract: This article summarizes the PISA international assessment program research and chemistry from science International evaluation programs PISA tests make up methodology and from him education in the process use about data given.

Key words PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS, TALIS, porcelain flower, ethylene, tobacco smoke, lighting gas.

At school received knowledge of a person upcoming life way determines. Many people knowledge price with measures. But price knowledge determiner sure criterion not. He students to activity encouraging, encouraging just a tool. Har one of the teacher own the work method, assessment method there is Which one teacher for price this is an incentive or student 45 minutes holding stand up tool. PISA 15 years old of students literacy and competence appraiser international program is, International Economical cooperation and development organization by in 3 years one times will be held. In it of students knowledge quality reading, mathematics and natural sciences will be monitored and 1000 points in the system is evaluated. This international program in 1997 work released for the first time in 2000 in practice applied. Current period school of graduates preparation level how to be necessity about views changed is going School of students sciences according to knowledge and skills formation with one in line own knowledge different vital situations apply get qualification ensuring revolutionization necessary. In the future this skills school of the graduate society in his life active to participate, the whole life during knowledge by increasing to go help gives Uzbekistan Republic Ministers December 8, 2018 education in the system education quality evaluation in the field international studies organize reach measures in the decision No. 997 on PIRLS (primary 4th grade students the text reading and to understand level assessment), TIMSS (4th and 8th grade students mathematics and natural direction from the sciences appropriation level evaluation), PISA (15-year-old of students reading, mathematics and natural direction the level of literacy in subjects evaluation), TALIS (leader and pedagogue of personnel common medium education in institutions teaching and education get environment and of teachers the work

conditions learning such as international evaluation programs according to international studies organize reach marked. [1; 223-224 b] Natural sciences Literacy is a person natural sciences development and their achievements use with depends in matters active citizenship position take over ability. In research evaluated natural sciences literacy according to knowledge and skills at school natural sciences, physics (astronomy elements with), biology, chemistry, geography sciences while being taught is formed. Research purpose skill and concepts complex from checking consists of Main attention, offer done to questions of students natural from the sciences received knowledge through answer to be given information based on scientific in terms of based on conclusions release ability is directed. To the students present done vital situations each one of a person personal in his life surface coming current problems with depends will be

Today's PISA tests per day all sciences like chemistry is also important in science place holds. Such tests in students clear, logical thinking, creativity, process or event-state sure imagination to do enable gives Agency (PIIMA) in the name of Ibn Sina chemistry and biology to the sciences specialized of the boarding school chemistry science teacher, expert, Jasurbek Kurbanov by created 300 PISA tests own into received manual not only specialized schools, maybe all general education schools, academic lyceums students too much for useful is considered Manual seventh class textbook based on prepared with table, graph, picture makes sense tests own into received.

To chemistry from the Pisa tests samples we bring

"In the greenhouse chemistry"

Ethylene substance anesthetic property in 1908 one great from the event after knowing received. Flower seller From Chicago florist china the flowers shut down to stay event after observing Him determination in order he is a botanist scientist offer reached Flowers to sleep greenhouse as the cause from the corner separate outgoing one unknown found to be gas.

QUESTION 1. Illuminator gas basis which gas organize that it will determined?

QUESTION 2. Ethylene the flower put to sleep to put mechanism explaining give?

QUESTION 3. Surgery in medicine in operations common narcosis is also used as?

Oil again work through and natural from gas a lot amount cheap ethylene is taken.

Ethylene is very wide biological to the effect have has been the first gaseous plant hormone. Ethylene of plants life rotation in the process different different functions does it, that's it including of seedlings development control make, of fruits ripening (especially fruits), buds opening (blooming process), leaves and of flowers aging and fall.

“Mendeleev and his friends”

From the days one day Mendeleev himself friends with long chatting from sitting then a little heart to open in order to in the air tobacco the smoke never how without difficulty empty to the jar collect to get said. Then a friend Repin a cigarette smoking tobacco the smoke into the air released when he is on the table empty of the jar mouth glass plate with closes. One little time pass with a miracle happened giving, empty closed jar white-tobacco smoke with paid. Then Mendeleev is a friend Repin smell to see offer is enough Repin without believing in the container the smoke smell with himself from the vessel quickly take running away strong cough starts

QUESTION 1: This event the reason chemical in terms of determination find the way and event explain ?

QUESTION 2: Mendeleev's friends which experience through distracted was You are also in your laboratory this the experience done enough conclusion take out

QUESTION 3: What because of a person consciousness when you lose the use of alcohol reasons biological in terms of explain ?

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